

Citation analysis of social work ETDs available at Tata Institute of Social Sciences (TISS), Mumbai @IR from 2001 to 2019: A study.

Abstract. The current study presents an analysis of the 16972 citations in the Social Work of 79 ETDs available at TISS, Mumbai @IR during the period 2001 to 2019. The EDTs of Social Work were analyzed to understand how the references sources have changed, once the internet reduced the search cost and efforts for citing the reference sources with the advent of latest tools availability. The findings reveal a striking contrast in terms of sources of references used by the students' pre and post internet era. The first ranking journal 'Economic and Political Weekly' has been cited 450 times.

1. Preamble

Citation analysis has been utilized by the scientists of Library and Information Science (LIS) as an apparatus to understand writing in a particular field of study and reveal how research has evolved through the cross-disciplinary engagement of ideas. It is a bibliometric procedure that utilizes the reference designs in the report to follow the connection between those archives with their unique sources and creators. It helps in distinguishing the key journals, and researchers. Lots of studies have been conducted around citation analysis by researchers all across the world, especially by library professionals. Accordingly, in the undergoing study, citation analysis has been carried out for Social Work 79 ETDs available at Shodhganga, INFLIBNET Centre and TISS, Mumbai @IR, DSpace, S.D.T.M. Library from 2001 to 2019.

Table 1. Year-wise distribution of Social Work ETDs available at TISS, Mumbai @IR from 2001 to 2019.

Year	No. of ETD	Percentage (%)	Year (Average:2010)	No. of ETD (Average:4.15)	Percentage (%) (Average:5.26)
2001	2	2.53	2011	4	5.07
2002	1	1.27	2012	4	5.07
2003	0	0	2013	12	15.18
2004	0	0	2014	4	5.07

2005	2	2.53	2015	11	13.92
2006	1	1.27	2016	10	12.65
2007	2	2.53	2017	9	11.39
2008	1	1.27	2018	6	7.6
2009	0	0	2019	8	10.12
2010	2	2.53			
Total				79	100
<i>Source: own analysis of data sourced from Shodhganga, INFLIBNET Centre and SDTM Library, TISS Mumbai.</i>					

Description:

Table 1: The current revise explains that as per according to the total number of year-wise distribution of 79 ETDs available in Social Work @IR, TISS, Mumbai or Shodhganga, INFLIBNET Centre during the period 2001 to 2019, the highest number of ETDs i.e. 12 (15.18%) was awarded in the year 2013 pursued by 2015 (11 ETDs awarded average 13.92%) and 2016 (10 ETDs awarded average 12.65%). Generally results visibly signify that highest numbers of 13 ETDs were awarded in Social Work during 2013. At the least 1 ETD was awarded in Social work in the year 2002, 2006 and 2008 (Single-single ETD awarded average 1.27%).

Table 2. Average total number of citations each year-wise ETDs

(Each Thesis Average) S.N.	Year	No. of Ph.D Theses (Average 4.15)	No. of Citations (Average 893.26)	No. of Citation - Each Thesis (Average)
01.	2001	2	392	196
02.	2002	1	340	340
03.	2003	0	0	0
04.	2004	0	0	0
05.	2005	2	417	208.5
06.	2006	1	590	590
07.	2007	2	640	320
08.	2008	1	180	180
09.	2009	0	0	0
10.	2010	2	337	168.5
11.	2011	4	752	188
12.	2012	4	1127	281.75
13.	2013	12	2609	217.41
14.	2014	4	758	189.5
15.	2015	11	2179	198.09
16.	2016	10	1885	188.5
17.	2017	9	2165	240.55

18.	2018	6	1168	194.66
19.	2019	8	1433	179.12
Total		79	16972	214.83
<i>Source: own analysis of data sourced from Shodhganga, INFLIBNET Centre and SDTM Library, TISS Mumbai.</i>				

Description:

Table 2. The present study shows that the year-wise allotment of highest 12 ETDs available in Social Work cited 2609 (Average 217.41), the identical absolute number of references and the normal number of references every thesis. The present study shows that significant dissimilarity be real with the ETDs available for the period of 2001 to 2019. This is found out that a total of 16972 citations scattered above 79 ETDs (4.15 citations average). This is found that the rate of citations of theses has viewed the growing movement. The outcome points that the average number of citations obtained each thesis is maximum in 2006 (590 citations each thesis) pursued by 340 citations each thesis in 2002. The generally average citation each thesis is 180 has been found out in the perusal by 2008.

Fig. 1. Bibliographic forms of literature cited in a rank order during 2001 to 2019.

Description:

Fig. 1. The present study shows that list of rank order for bibliographic forms of literature cited of ETDs available in Social Work by TISS, Mumbai @IR during the period 2001 to 2019. The current investigation shows as: Journals confirmed for 6384 citations (37.62%); Books and Monographs confirmed for 5742 citations (33.84%); Web Resources confirmed for 2031 citations (11.97%); Reports confirmed for 1779 citations (10.49%); Working Paper confirmed for 220 citations (1.3%); Newspaper confirmed for 210 citations (1.24%); Govt. Reports confirmed for 173 citations (1.02%); Theses and Dissertations confirmed for 172 citations (1.01%); Conference Proceedings confirmed for 78 citations (0.45%); Encyclopaedia Book confirmed for 68 citations (0.4); Census/NSSO Dataset

confirmed for 49 citations (0.28%); Magazine confirmed for 45 citations (0.26%); Year Book and Pamphlet confirmed for 2 citations (0.005%); and Not Identified (N.I.) confirmed for 19 citations (0.11%).

2. Findings and Conclusion

In the study is an analysis of the 16972 citations in the Social Work of 79 ETDs available at @IR, Tata Institute of Social Sciences (TISS), Mumbai or Shodhganga during the period 2001 to 2019. The information gathered utilizing for ETDs Shodhganga and @IR, DSpace, SDTM Library, TISS, Mumbai. The investigation completed for boundaries, for example, period of references, bibliographical arrangement, and title of pages, unique and references of each thesis. The softcopy and printed copies were inspected concerning name of the references, number of references, title of thesis in social work, year-wise of thesis submitted, sorts of works referred to, branch of knowledge secured and the complete of each referred to work. This work has been executed for reference assessment of 79 ETDs submitted in social work by TISS, Mumbai and gives accommodating bits of knowledge into the report types, the dispersion of nation/domains, the circulation of foundations, the geological conveyance of creators, the most dynamic creators and their assessment advantages or fields, the co-initiation arrange and worldwide/nearby participation. This paper additionally gives important data about the center chronicled references and the most smoking new papers through co-reference investigation and reference analysis. List of first ranking journal 'Economic and Political Weekly (EPW)' has been cited 450 times.

Acknowledgement

Special thanks to the co-author, R. Sarangapani (Ph.D. Supervisor), University Librarian/Head i/c., Arignar Anna Central Library, Department of Library and Information Science (Deptt. of LIS), Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India, for granting permission to publish this manuscript.

References

1. Verma, B. K., & Sarangapani, R., (2020). Citation Analysis of Ph.D Theses Awarded in Social Work by Tata Institute of Social Sciences (TISS), Mumbai: A Study before the Internet Era. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, published by Libraries at University of Nebraska-Lincoln (LPP 'e-journal'-University of Nebraska, USA- SCOPUS Indexed-UGCCARE-Group - 'A' Journal); ISSN 1522-0222, Vol.22, Issue No.-4, Page Nos. 1-16. Available at <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/334983692.pdf>
2. Verma, B. K., & Sarangapani, R., (2020). Citation Analysis of Ph.D Theses Awarded in Social Work by Tata Institute of Social Sciences (TISS), Mumbai during Up to 1985: A study. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Cycle Research (JICR); An UGC-CARE Approved Group-II Journal (Scopus Indexed Till 1993), XII (I), 1110-1117.* doi: 18.0002.JICR.2020.V12I1.008301.316901 Available at <http://www.jicrjournal.com/gallery/120-jicr-january-2395.pdf>
3. Verma, B.K., & Sarangapani, R., (2019). Literature Review in the field of Citation Analysis: a study. 'Reshaping Librarianship Innovations and Transformations (ICRLIT-2019: e-Proceedings)' organized by AACL, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India, Pg.380-391. Available at <https://cdn.b-u.ac.in/notification/may19/library2019.pdf>